

Application of compositional data analysis to biogeochemical exploration for disclosing the lithology-derived signatures in plants from its physiological artifacts

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In the early stages of mineral exploration, biogeochemical data of plants can provide a cost-effective and efficient insight into the underlying lithology. Plants accumulate certain element groups differently in their tissue types - specific to the physiological function of plant organs. This leads to substantial variability in elements of interest between tissue types (needles, twigs, bark) of plant species, not only in terms of their concentration ranges but also in terms of their element ratios. This work aims to investigate the multivariate relative relationships of elements and element groups to reveal patterns in biogeochemical data related to bedrock lithology and geochemistry. The ultimate goal would be to discover element ratios such that the contribution of plant species and tissue types (noise) could be minimized by appropriate normalization of the plant data.

To reach the aim of the study we investigate plant geochemical data by using compositional data analysis techniques. In this case study, a biogeochemical data set collected in Northern Finland was used. The data consist of geochemical analyses of several species acquired on top of mineralized rocks of several types and their surrounding barren rocks. The biogeochemical data were normalized via perturbation by the inverse of the center, i.e., by removing the mean. The center was calculated by taking the compositional mean of the samples collected over the barren sites for each species and tissue type group to represent the baseline contribution by the physiological effects of a species/tissue type. For each sample, the centering was applied according to its species and tissue type separately by applying the corresponding mean. Application examples for the biogeochemical data show that the approach is successful in removing the plant's inherent signature so that only the remnant variability of the pattern is left for interpretation. The results of the data exploratory methods show that the variability after the normalization corresponds to the geological features such as underlying mineral deposits. This approach helps to reveal biogeochemical signatures originating from bedrock geology.